

Calculation of grand partition function (gpf) of the symmetric and asymmetric double well potential by using path-integral based thermal cluster cumulant (PI-TCC) method

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Abstract : In this paper, the grand partition function of symmetric and asymmetric double well potential is calculated by using Path-Integral based Thermal Cluster Cumulant (PI-TCC) method developed by us. This method like Feynman path-integral representation treats the cyclical path $x(\tau)$ as a Fourier series with a sum of a classical centroid point, x_0 and a fluctuation variable, $y(\tau)$. Then, $y(\tau)$ is treated as a field variable. The contribution of the fluctuation component of the grand partition function (gpf) around x_0 is related to the y -average with respect to the y -dependent optimized Gaussian path-integral measure of an evolution operator, $U_I(\tau)$ which satisfy an equation of motion in imaginary-time around x_0 . In the PI-representation, $U_I(\tau)$ is generically T -ordered product of $y(\tau)$ -variables. So, the y -average of $U_I(\tau)$, denoted as $\langle U_I(\tau) \rangle_y$, is computed by utilising the concept of a Wick-like reordering theorem that needs the new concept of y -normal ordering and y -contraction. Then, the quantity $\langle U_I(\tau) \rangle_y$ is computed nonperturbatively by using a y -normal ordered exponential cluster cumulant ansatz for $U_I(\tau)$ involving both the operator cumulant with y variables and the number cumulant. Now, $\langle U_I(\tau) \rangle_y$ becomes exponential of only the number cumulant simply because by definition y -average of y -normal ordered product of operators vanishes. Finally, the grand partition function (gpf) is computed by integration over the x_0 variables in the range for which the integrand almost vanishes at $-x_0$ and at $+x_0$.

Keywords : Grand partition function, path-integral thermal cluster cumulant (PI-TCC) method, optimized Gaussian path-integral measure, Wick-like reordering theorem, normal ordering, contraction, exponential cluster cumulant Ansatz, double well potential.

Introduction

The computation of the grand partition function (gpf), Z_q of double well potentials at finite temperature provides us with all other thermally averaged equilibrium properties of them such as density of states, free energies, etc.¹. The expression for the grand partition function in general is given by

$$Z_q = \text{Tr} e^{-\beta(H-\mu N)} = \text{Tr} e^{-\beta H} = \sum_i e^{-\beta E_i} \quad (1)$$

where E_i 's are the eigenvalues of the hamiltonian, H and $\beta = 1/T$, T being the temperature. In the above eq. (1), the constraint, μ is set to zero without destroying the generality of the methodology. Most of the existing methods bypass the above sum-over states approach which needs the knowledge of the robust energy spectrum of the

total hamiltonian of the system particularly when the number of degrees of freedom is high. It is convenient to exploit in one form or another the striking algebraic similarity of the Boltzmann statistical operator $e^{-\beta H}$ for the equilibrium partition function and the Heisenberg time-evolution operator e^{-iHt} , t being the real-time. This allows one to treat the Boltzmann operator to be treated as an evolution operator in imaginary-time, $\tau (= it)$ as shown below :

$$-\frac{\partial U(\tau)}{\partial \tau} = HU(\tau) \quad (2)$$

where H is a hamiltonian of the system and $U(\tau) = e^{-\tau H}$. The question is how to compute $U(\beta)$, where β is a specified inverse temperature?

The most commonly used approach for treating ther-

mal averages is to invoke a perturbative treatment of the Boltzmann operator by partitioning the hamiltonian into a convenient unperturbed component H_0 and a perturbation $V(\tau)$, i.e. $H = H_0 + V(\tau)$ and usually $[H_0, V(\tau)] \neq 0$. If we represent $U(\tau) = U_0(\tau) U_I(\tau)$ with $U_0(\tau) = e^{-\tau H_0}$ and substitute it in eq. (2), then we have an evolution equation of $U_I(\tau)$ given by

$$-\frac{\partial U_I(\tau)}{\partial \tau} = V_I(\tau) U_I(\tau) \quad (3)$$

where $V_I(\tau) = e^{\tau H_0} V e^{-\tau H_0}$ is the interaction representation of V .

The formal solution of eq. (3) is given by

$$U_I(\tau) = T \exp \left[-\int_0^\tau V_I(\tau') d\tau' \right] \quad (4)$$

with $U_I(0) = 1$ and T is the τ -ordering operator². Therefore, we obtain

$$U_I(\beta) = T \exp \left[-\int_0^\beta V_I(\tau') d\tau' \right] \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} U(\beta) &= e^{-\beta H_0} \times T \exp \left[-\int_0^\beta V_I(\tau') d\tau' \right] \\ &= e^{-\beta H_0} \times U_I(\beta) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Now, let us see what is the statistical average $\langle U_I(\beta) \rangle_0$ with respect to unperturbed H_0 ? In statistical mechanics, the average of a quantity A is given by

$$\langle A \rangle_0 = \frac{\text{Tr } e^{-\beta H_0} A}{\text{Tr } e^{-\beta H_0}} = \frac{\text{Tr } e^{-\beta H_0} A}{Z_{0q}} \quad (7)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle_0$ denotes averaging with respect to H_0 , and Z_{0q} is the unperturbed partition function given by

$$Z_{0q} = \text{Tr } e^{-\beta H_0} = \sum_i e^{-\beta E_i^0} \quad (8)$$

Therefore, using eqs. (6) and (7) one can write $\langle U_I(\beta) \rangle_0$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle U_I(\beta) \rangle_0 &= \frac{\text{Tr } e^{-\beta H_0} U_I(\beta)}{\text{Tr } e^{-\beta H_0}} = \frac{\text{Tr } U(\beta)}{\text{Tr } U_0(\beta)} \\ &= \left\langle T \exp \left[-\int_0^\beta V_I(\tau') d\tau' \right] \right\rangle_0 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{Z_q}{Z_{0q}} \quad (9)$$

From eq. (9), we can evaluate Z_q as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_q &= Z_{0q} \times \langle U_I(\beta) \rangle_0 \\ &= Z_{0q} \times \left[1 - \int_0^\beta \langle V_I(\tau') \rangle_0 d\tau' + \frac{1}{2!} \int_0^\beta d\tau' \int_0^\beta d\tau'' \langle T[V_I(\tau') V_I(\tau'')] \rangle_0 - \dots \right] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

But we know that the partition function Z_q has a multiplicatively separable property and hence the free energy F_q is additively separable. Let us check wheather the eq. (10) preserves those properties or not. Let us consider a composite system $A-B$ whose partition function $[Z_q]_{AB}$ by using eq. (1) can be written as

$$[Z_q]_{AB} = [Z_q]_A \times [Z_q]_B \quad (11)$$

and the corresponding free energy, $[F_q]_{AB}$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [F_q]_{AB} &= -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln ([Z_q]_A \times [Z_q]_B) \\ &= [F_q]_A + [F_q]_B \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where for arbitrary system X , $[F_q]_X$ is given by

$$[F_q]_X = \frac{1}{\beta} \ln [Z_q]_X \quad (13)$$

The question is wheather the properties in eqs. (11) and (12) are satisfied in the perturbative scheme? The answer is simply not. This is because from eq. (10) the expression of partition function of $A-B$ composite system upto power '1' of V is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [Z_q]_{AB}^{(1)} &= [Z_{0q}]_A \times [Z_{0q}]_B \times \left[-\int_0^\beta \langle [V_I(\tau')]_A \rangle_0 d\tau' \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_0^\beta \langle [V_I(\tau')]_B \rangle_0 d\tau' \right] \\ &= [Z_{0q}]_A \times [Z_{0q}]_B \times [C_A + C_B] \\ &= [Z_{0q}]_{AB} \times [C_A + C_B] \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where for arbitrary system X , the first order correlation correction term, C_X is given by

$$C_X = -\int_0^\beta \langle [V_I(\tau')]_X \rangle_0 d\tau' \quad (15)$$

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and the corresponding expression for the free energy is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [F_q]_{AB}^{(1)} &= -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln [Z_q]_{AB}^{(1)} \\ &= [F_{0q}]_A + [F_{0q}]_B - \frac{1}{\beta} \ln [C_A + C_B] \\ &= [F_{0q}]_{AB} - \frac{1}{\beta} \ln [C_A + C_B] \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $\ln [C_A + C_B]$ is mixed power series in C_A and C_B . So, $[F_q]_{AB}^{(1)}$ is not additively separable as in eq. (12). Now, the question is how to overcome this problem? The answer is simply to represent the ratio $[Z_q]_{AB}/[Z_{0q}]_{AB}$ upto ' n '-th power of V as

$$\left(\frac{[Z_q]_{AB}}{[Z_{0q}]_{AB}} \right)^{(n)} = e^{K^{(0)} + K^{(1)} + K^{(2)} + \dots + K^{(n)}} \quad (17)$$

with

$$K^{(0)} = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$K^{(1)} = -\int_0^\beta \langle [V_I(\tau')]_A \rangle_0 d\tau' - \int_0^\beta \langle [V_I(\tau')]_B \rangle_0 d\tau' \quad (19)$$

$$\begin{aligned} K^{(2)} &= +\frac{1}{2!} \int_0^\beta d\tau' \int_0^\beta d\tau'' \langle T[[V_I(\tau')]_A [V_I(\tau'')]_A] \rangle_0 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2!} \left[\int_0^\beta \langle [V_I(\tau')]_A \rangle_0 d\tau' \right]^2 + \dots \\ &= +\frac{1}{2!} \int_0^\beta d\tau' \int_0^\beta d\tau'' \langle T[[V_I(\tau')]_A \\ &\quad [V_I(\tau'')]_A] \rangle_0^{\text{connected}} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Eqs. (18), (19) and (20) show that the exponents K remain connected at each order of perturbation so that the logarithm of Z_q now generates an extensive free energy as shown below. The quantity in the exponent is called cumulant³. Let us consider the first order expression of the ratio $[Z_q]_{AB}/[Z_{0q}]_{AB}$ given by

$$\left(\frac{[Z_q]_{AB}}{[Z_{0q}]_{AB}} \right)^{(1)} = e^{K^{(1)}} \quad (21)$$

Using eq. (19), we have from eq. (21)

$$\left(\frac{[Z_q]_{AB}}{[Z_{0q}]_{AB}} \right)^{(1)} = e^{[C_A + C_B]} \quad (22)$$

This leads to the expression of partition function of the A - B composite system corrected upto first order as

$$\begin{aligned} [Z_q]_{AB}^{(1)} &= [Z_{0q}]_{AB} \times e^{[C_A + C_B]} \\ &= ([Z_{0q}]_A e^{C_A}) \times ([Z_{0q}]_B e^{C_B}) \\ &= [Z_q]_A^{(1)} \times [Z_q]_B^{(1)} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where $[Z_q]_A^{(1)}$ and $[Z_q]_B^{(1)}$ are the partition functions corrected upto first order of V of the system A and B respectively.

Therefore, the expression for the first order free energy is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [F_q]_{AB}^{(1)} &= -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln [Z_q]_{AB}^{(1)} \\ &= -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln [Z_{0q}]_{AB} - \frac{1}{\beta} [C_A + C_B] \\ &= [F_{0q}]_{AB} - \frac{1}{\beta} [C_A + C_B] \\ &= \left([F_{0q}]_A - \frac{1}{\beta} C_A \right) + \left([F_{0q}]_B - \frac{1}{\beta} C_B \right) \\ &= [F_q]_A^{(1)} + [F_q]_B^{(1)} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where $[F_q]_A^{(1)}$ and $[F_q]_B^{(1)}$ are the free energies corrected upto first order of V of the system A and B respectively. Note that unlike ordinary perturbative scheme, the above perturbative cumulant expansion method maintains the size-extensivity of the observable properties of the A - B composite system. But the convergence of both the methodologies are not so satisfactory in the strong coupling regime due to the perturbative nature of them.

The question is how to overcome this poor coverage of the above perturbative scheme? The answer is to embark on to a methodology that demands nonperturbative access to the cumulants. In order to achieve it, let us posit an exponential ansatz for $U_I(\beta)$ given by

$$U_I(\beta) = e^{K(\beta)} \quad (25)$$

where $K(\beta)$ contains both the creation and the annihilation operators as well as the number. Now plugging it in

eq. (9), we have

$$\frac{Z_q}{Z_{0q}} = \langle U_I(\beta) \rangle_0 = \langle e^{K(\beta)} \rangle_0 \quad (26)$$

Note that if we represent the hamiltonian in the second quantized form, then K will contain both the operator and the number.

Now substitute the eq. (25) into the eq. (3) with β as the imaginary-time variable, τ , we have

$$-\frac{\partial e^{K(\tau)}}{\partial \tau} = V_I(\tau) e^{K(\tau)} \quad (27)$$

But $K(\tau)$ is a sum of τ -ordered products of operators. So, the left hand side can be evaluated by using Magnus expansion formula that is a complicated series⁴ given by

$$-\frac{de^{\hat{A}}}{dt} = \left[\frac{e^{\hat{A}} - 1}{\hat{A}} \hat{A} e^{\hat{A}} \right] \quad (28)$$

where $\hat{A}C = [\hat{A}, C]$. On the right hand side of eq. (27) we also land with a complicated series containing non-commuting operator products. Then, we solve the coupled equations obtained by equating K 's having equal operator rank from both sides. Finally, one can evaluate $\langle e^{K(\beta)} \rangle$ as a complicated expression.

The question is how to overcome these difficulties? The viable strategy of resolving it is to posit a thermal normal ordered exponential ansatz for $U_I(\tau)$ given by^{5,6}

$$U_I(\tau) = \{e^{K(\tau)}\}_\beta \quad (29)$$

where $\{\dots\}_\beta$ represents thermal normal ordering of operators with respect to a suitable thermal vacuum, $|0_\beta\rangle$ and within this normal ordering symbol the operators behave as ordinary variables so that now we have unlike eq. (27) more simplified equation given by

$$-\left\{ \frac{\partial K(\tau)}{\partial \tau} e^{K(\tau)} \right\}_\beta = \{V_I(\tau)\}_\beta \{e^{K(\tau)}\}_\beta \quad (30)$$

where $\{V_I(\tau)\}_\beta$ represents that the hamiltonian is written in thermal normal order. Note that in order to evaluate the thermal trace in a compact manner it is now necessary to develop field-theoretic tools like Thermal Wick's Theorem analogues to zero-temperature Wick's Theorem².

Let us expand $K(\tau)$ as

$$K(\tau) = \sum_{m,n} K_{m,n}(\tau) (a^\dagger)^m (a)^n \quad (31)$$

where a^\dagger and a are the creation and annihilation operators and $K_{m,n}(\tau)$ is called operator amplitude/cluster amplitude with m, n are the rank of creation and annihilation operator.

Let us plug eq. (31) into the eq. (30) and apply thermal field theoretic tools^{5,6} in the resulting equation and then equate $K_{m,n}(\tau)$'s of the same rank from both sides. This leads to the two sets of differential equations given by

$$-\left(\frac{\partial K_{m,n}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} \right)_\beta^{(m,n)} = \left\{ \overline{V_I(\tau) e^{K(\tau)}} \right\}_\beta^{(m,n)} \quad (32)$$

$$-\left(\frac{\partial K_{0,0}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} \right)_\beta^{0,0} = \left\{ \overline{V_I(\tau) e^{K(\tau)}} \right\}_\beta^{0,0} \quad (33)$$

where $\left\{ \overline{V e^K} \right\}_\beta$ represents thermal contraction. The eqs. (32) and (33) are called Thermal Cluster Cumulant (TCC) equations^{5,6} and are coupled to each other. Solving these equations by integrating up to β we obtain the number component of $K_{0,0}(\beta)$ that includes the contribution of other $K_{m,n}(\beta)$'s simply because the equations are all coupled.

Thus from eq. (26), we obtain

$$\frac{Z_q}{Z_{0q}} = \langle U_I(\beta) \rangle_0 = \langle e^{K_{0,0}(\beta)} \rangle_0 \quad (34)$$

Note that the deviation of the Z_q value from the exact value Z_q^{exact} increases as the temperature is increased for a given rank of cluster cumulant operators. This can be improved by including higher rank of cluster cumulant operators that necessitates to solve more number of equations.

In order to increase the efficiency of the TCC method, we have developed a path-integral based thermal cluster cumulant (PI-TCC) method⁷ that started from the Feynman's path-integral representation for computing thermal trace of Boltzmann statistical operator. This will be discussed in the next sections.

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Path-integral based TCC (PI-TCC) method for calculating thermal trace of Boltzmann statistical operator, $e^{-\beta H}$

The path-integral representation of eq. (1) in coordinate representation is given by

$$Z_q = \text{Tr} e^{-\beta H} = \int dx \langle x | e^{-\beta H} | x \rangle \quad (35)$$

which in turn be written as¹

$$Z_q = \oint D[x] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2(\tau) + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0^2 x^2(\tau) + V[x(\tau)] \right] d\tau \right) \quad (36)$$

where \oint denotes path-integration over all cyclical paths, $x(\tau)$ denotes quantum paths periodic in β and $V[x(\tau)]$ is a polynomial in $x(\tau)$. Clearly, with Z_{0q} defined as

$$Z_{0q} = \oint D[x(\tau)] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{1}{2} \dot{x}^2(\tau) + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0^2 x^2(\tau) \right] d\tau \right) \quad (37)$$

one can write Z_q/Z_{0q} as an average

$$\frac{Z_q}{Z_{0q}} = \left\langle \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta V[x(\tau)] d\tau \right) \right\rangle \quad (38)$$

where the average has to be interpreted as the ratio obtained from eqs. (36) and (37).

In the PI representation, one can write the cyclical path $x(\tau)$ as a Fourier series involving the Fourier components x_m :

$$\begin{aligned} x(\tau) &= x_0 + y(\tau) = x_0 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (x_m e^{i\Omega_m \tau} + c.c.) \\ &= x_0 + y(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

where $\Omega_m = (2\pi m/\beta)$ is the m -th Fourier harmonic of a fundamental harmonic frequency $\Omega_1 = (2\pi/\beta)$. The frequencies Ω_m are the Matsubara frequencies⁸, and $y(\tau)$ denotes the cyclical paths describing the quantum fluctuations around the centroid, x_0 , of each point of the quantum path $x(\tau)$. x_0 is given by

$$x_0 = \frac{1}{\beta} \int_0^\beta x(\tau) d\tau \quad (40)$$

and

$$\int_0^\beta y(\tau) d\tau = 0 \quad (41)$$

Let us split the variables $y(\tau)$, x_0 and $x(\tau)$ as shown below :

$$x_0 = x_{0+} + x_{0-}, \quad (42)$$

$$y(\tau) = y_+(\tau) + y_-(\tau), \quad (43)$$

$$\begin{aligned} x(\tau) &= x_+(\tau) + x_-(\tau) \\ &= x_{0+} + y_+(\tau) + x_{0-} + y_-(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Thus, the two-time correlation function is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle x(\tau_1)x(\tau_2) \rangle &= \langle x_{0+}x_{0-} \rangle + \langle x_{0-}x_{0+} \rangle \\ &\quad + \langle y_+(\tau_1)y_-(\tau_2) \rangle + \langle y_-(\tau_1)y_+(\tau_2) \rangle \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where

$$\langle x_{0+}x_{0-} \rangle = \langle x_{0-}x_{0+} \rangle = \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \left[\frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} \right] \quad (46)$$

$$\langle y_+(\tau_1)y_-(\tau_2) \rangle = \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m \neq 0} \frac{e^{-i\Omega_m(\tau_1-\tau_2)}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right] \quad (47)$$

$$\langle y_-(\tau_1)y_+(\tau_2) \rangle = \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m \neq 0} \frac{e^{-i\Omega_m(\tau_1-\tau_2)}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right] \quad (48)$$

In this connection, the two time correlation function, $G_f(\tau, \tau') [= \langle y(\tau)y(\tau') \rangle]$ of the fluctuation variable $y(\tau)$ is shown in details in the Appendix-A.

Using eq. (39) in eq. (36), we have

$$\begin{aligned} Z_q &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 \exp(-\beta V(x_0)) \\ &\quad \times \oint D[y] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + V(x_0 + y) - V(x_0) \right] d\tau \right) \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

Let us define the zeroth-order 'local' gpf for the fluctuation component (fgpf) as

$$\zeta_0(x_0) = \oint D[y] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 \right] d\tau \right) \quad (50)$$

and the perturbed counter part as

$$\zeta(x_0) = \oint D[y] \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 \right] + \left(- \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 + V(x_0 + y) - V(x_0) \right) d\tau \right) \quad (51)$$

where $\omega_0(x_0)$ is the ‘local’ reference frequency.

Then the ratio $\zeta(x_0)/\zeta_0(x_0)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta(x_0)}{\zeta_0(x_0)} &= \left\langle \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta \left[- \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 + \sum_{l \neq 0} \frac{1}{l!} \frac{\partial^l V[x_0, y]}{\partial x^l} \Big|_{x_0} y^l \right] d\tau \right) \right\rangle_y \\ &= \left\langle T \exp \left(- \int_0^\beta V_f[x_0, y(\tau)] d\tau \right) \right\rangle_y \\ &= \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y \quad (52) \end{aligned}$$

where $(\dots)_y$ denotes average with respect to the PI measure of y , called y -average hereafter. Here, we have chosen for the PI measure a ‘local’ reference harmonic frequency $\omega_0(x_0)$ at each centroid point x_0 . With respect to the y -average, the product of $y(\tau)$ ’s is shown to satisfy gaussian factorization property. One can in principle evaluate $\zeta(x_0)/\zeta_0(x_0)$ by means of cumulant expansion method³ as discussed in Section 1, but being perturbative in nature it is not suitable for systems with strong perturbation. Following Matsubara⁸, Bloch⁹, let us define y -normal ordered y -products, whose y -average vanishes with respect to PI-measure, and y -contractions with respect to the y -average. Using these field theoretic tools, we have de-

rived a Wick-like expansion formula for evaluating the y -average of the product of string of $y(\tau)$ variables¹⁰. Now, we can express the T -ordered exponential in eq. (52) as a y -normal ordered one in a manner exactly analogous to the TCC method^{5,6}.

From eq. (52), we can write

$$- \frac{\partial U(\tau)}{\partial \tau} = V_f[x_0, y(\tau)] U(\tau) \quad (53)$$

Let us express $U(\tau)$ in terms of $U_{m,n}(\tau)$ where $U_{m,n}(\tau)$ has m number of y_+ and n number of y_- variables in normal order. Thus, we have the operator differential equation of the form

$$- \frac{\partial U_{m,n}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} = \sum_{pqkl} [[V_f[x_0, y(\tau)]]_{p,q} U_{k,l}(\tau)]_{m,n} \quad (54)$$

where $[V_f[x_0, y(\tau)]]_{p,q}$ has p number of y_+ and q number of y_- variables in normal order. $[\dots]_{m,n}$ denotes that the m, n component of the composite has to be taken. Let us use the Wick-like expansion formula¹⁰ developed by us for the right side of eq. (54). This leads to the equations for $U_{m,n}$ which contains in its right side all the composites $[V_f[x_0, y(\tau)]]_{p,q} U_{k,l}$ having contractions such that the number of uncontracted y_+ and y_- variables are m and n respectively. Let us extract the corresponding amplitude components in eq. (54) having gaussian quantum variables, y_+, y_- , via a quantum analogue of what is known as Novikov’s theorem¹¹ explicitly shown in Appendix-B.

Let us illustrate how to extract the amplitude part of $U_{m,n}(\tau)$ by using generalized Novikov’s theorem as shown in Appendix-B. Considering the case of $U_{1,1}(\tau)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \{y_+(T)y_-(T)\} U_{1,1}(\tau) \rangle_y &= \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 G_f^+(T - \tau_1) \times \\ &G_f^-(\tau_2 - T) \times \\ &\frac{\delta^2 U_{1,1}(\tau)}{\delta y_-(\tau_1) \delta y_+(\tau_2)} \quad \forall T > \tau \quad (55) \end{aligned}$$

where the propagator $G_f^+(T - \tau_1) (\equiv \langle y_+(T)y_-(\tau_1) \rangle)$ and $G_f^-(\tau_2 - T) (\equiv \langle y_-(\tau_2)y_+(T) \rangle)$ are *not factorizable* into factors containing separately the time arguments, which is essential for the development of TCC. This situation can simply be handled by writing them as differences be-

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tween a quantum propagator and a classical propagator as

$$\begin{aligned} G_f^+(T - \tau_1) &= G_q^+(T - \tau_1) - G_c^+ \\ &= n_q \exp [\omega_0(x_0)(T - \tau_1)] - G_c^+ \end{aligned} \quad (56)$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_f^-(\tau_2 - T) &= G_q^-(\tau_2 - T) - G_c^- \\ &= (n_q + 1) \exp [\omega_0(x_0)(\tau_2 - T)] - G_c^- \end{aligned} \quad (57)$$

where $n_q = [\exp (\beta \omega_0(x_0)) - 1]^{-1}$ and $G_c^+ = G_c^- = [\beta \omega_0(x_0)]^{-1} = n_c$. This is shown in Appendix-A. This type of manipulation leads eq. (55) to the form

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \{y_+(T)y_-(T)\} U_{1,1}(T) \rangle_y &= n_q(n_q + 1)\chi_{1,1}^{0,0} - n_q n_c \chi_{0,1}^{1,0} \\ &\quad - (n_q + 1)n_c \chi_{1,0}^{0,1} \\ &\quad + n_c^2 \chi_{0,0}^{1,1} \end{aligned} \quad (58)$$

where

$$\chi_{1,1}^{0,0} = \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 e^{-\omega_0(x_0)(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \frac{\delta^2 U_{1,1}(\tau)}{\delta y_-(\tau_1) \delta y_+(\tau_2)} \quad (59)$$

$$\chi_{0,1}^{1,0} = \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 e^{-\omega_0(x_0)(T - \tau_1)} \frac{\delta^2 U_{1,1}(\tau)}{\delta y_-(\tau_1) \delta y_+(\tau_2)} \quad (60)$$

$$\chi_{1,0}^{0,1} = \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 e^{\omega_0(x_0)(\tau_2 - T)} \frac{\delta^2 U_{1,1}(\tau)}{\delta y_-(\tau_1) \delta y_+(\tau_2)} \quad (61)$$

$$\chi_{0,0}^{1,1} = \int d\tau_1 d\tau_2 \frac{\delta^2 U_{1,1}(\tau)}{\delta y_-(\tau_1) \delta y_+(\tau_2)} \quad (62)$$

The above replacement of the fluctuation propagators by differences of quantum and classical propagators can be looked upon as shown in Appendix-A involving the new quantum variables (\bar{x}_\pm) and the classical variables ($\bar{x}_{0\pm}$) defined as $\bar{x}_\pm(0) = \sqrt{2\omega_0(x_0)} x_\pm(0)$ and $\bar{x}_{0\pm}(0) = \sqrt{2\omega_0(x_0)} x_{0\pm}(0)$ corresponding to certain x_0 -dependent quantum mechanical creation/annihilation operators and its classical counterparts, respectively. With the help of them, eq. (58) can be faithfully reproduced by representing $U_{1,1}(\tau)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} U_{1,1}(\tau) &= \{\bar{x}_+(0)\bar{x}_-(0)\} \chi_{1,1}^{0,0} + \{\bar{x}_+(0)\bar{x}_{0-}(0)\} \chi_{1,0}^{0,1} \\ &\quad + \{\bar{x}_{0+}(0)\bar{x}_-(0)\} \chi_{0,1}^{1,0} \\ &\quad + \{\bar{x}_{0+}(0)\bar{x}_{0-}(0)\} \chi_{0,0}^{1,1} \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

Using eq. (63) in eq. (58), the following non-zero contractions are obtained

$$\langle \bar{x}_+(\tau_1)\bar{x}_-(\tau_2) \rangle = n_q e^{\omega_0(x_0)(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \quad (64)$$

$$\langle \bar{x}_-(\tau_1)\bar{x}_+(\tau_2) \rangle = (n_q + 1) e^{-\omega_0(x_0)(\tau_1 - \tau_2)} \quad (65)$$

$$\langle \bar{x}_{0+}(\tau_1)\bar{x}_{0-}(\tau_2) \rangle \equiv \langle \bar{x}_{0+}(0)\bar{x}_{0-}(0) \rangle = n_c \quad (66)$$

$$\langle \bar{x}_{0-}(\tau_1)\bar{x}_{0+}(\tau_2) \rangle \equiv \langle \bar{x}_{0-}(0)\bar{x}_{0+}(0) \rangle = n_c \quad (67)$$

In general, one can write eq. (63) for $U(\tau)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} U(\tau) &= \sum_{m,n,k,l} \frac{1}{m!} \frac{1}{n!} \frac{1}{k!} \frac{1}{l!} \\ &\quad \{\bar{x}_+(0)\bar{x}_-(0)\bar{x}_{0+}^k(0)\bar{x}_{0-}^l(0)\}_y \chi_{m,n}^{k,l} \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

Now, the question is how to get nonperturbative access to $\zeta(x_0)/\zeta_0(x_0) = \langle U(\beta) \rangle_y$? The answer is to rewrite the above linear expansion representation of $U(\tau)$ as a y -normal ordered exponential given by

$$U(\tau) = \{\exp(S_f + u_f)\}_y \quad (69)$$

where

$$S_f(\tau) = \sum_{m,n} S_{m,n}(\tau) \{y_+^m y_-^n\}_y \quad (70)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \{S_f^2(\tau)\} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{m1,n1 \\ m2,n2}} S_{m1,n1}(\tau) S_{m2,n2}(\tau) \\ &\quad \{y_+^{(m1+m2)} y_-^{(n1+n2)}\}_y \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

In terms of $\bar{x}_\pm(0)$ and $\bar{x}_{0\pm}(0)$ variables, we have

$$S_f(\tau) = \sum_{m,n,k,l} \{\bar{x}_+^m(0)\bar{x}_-^n(0)\bar{x}_{0+}^k(0)\bar{x}_{0-}^l(0)\}_y S_{m,n}^{k,l}(\tau) \quad (72)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \{S_f^2(\tau)\} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\substack{m1,n1,k1,l1 \\ m2,n2,k2,l2}} \{\bar{x}_+^{(m1+m2)}(0)\bar{x}_-^{(n1+n2)}(0) \\ &\quad \bar{x}_{0+}^{(k1+k2)}(0)\bar{x}_{0-}^{(l1+l2)}(0)\}_y \\ &\quad \times S_{m1,n1}^{k1,l1}(\tau) S_{m2,n2}^{k2,l2}(\tau) \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

In eq. (69), S_f is the operator part of $U(\tau)$; $u_f(\tau)$ is the purely number part. From eqs. (54) and (69), we can set up the PI-TCC equations given by

$$-\frac{\partial S_{m,n}^{k,l}[x_0, \tau]}{\partial \tau} = \left[\overline{\{V_f[x_0, y(\tau)] \exp(S_f(\tau))\}}_y \right]_{m,n}^{k,l} \quad (74)$$

$$-\frac{\partial u_f[x_0, \tau]}{\partial \tau} = \left\langle V_f[x_0, y(\tau)] \exp(S_f(\tau)) \right\rangle_y \quad (75)$$

where the right side of eq. (75) is the completely contracted component of $\langle V_f[x_0, y(\tau)] \exp(S_f(\tau)) \rangle_y$. In arriving at the contracted terms on the right sides of eqs. (74) and (75), we have made use of our Wick-like expansion formula¹⁰. We emphasize the advantage of normal ordered Ansatz which allows us to bypass the Magnus expansion procedure⁴ as shown in Section 1. Despite this, eqs. (74) and (75) respect the other advantages of our TCC theory^{5,6}.

The use of normal ordered exponential Ansatz in eq. (69) then reduced the ratio $\zeta(x_0)/\zeta_0(x_0)$ in eq. (52) to the form :

$$\frac{\zeta(x_0)}{\zeta_0(x_0)} = e^{u_f[x_0, \beta]} \quad (76)$$

where u_f depends on x_0 via the hamiltonian, appearing in the exponential of eq. (52), which depends on x_0 . Thus, having solved for $u_f[x_0, \beta]$, we get Z_q as

$$Z_q = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 e^{-\beta V_{\text{eff}}(x_0)} \quad (77)$$

where the nonperturbative effective potential $V_{\text{eff}}(x_0)$ is given by

$$V_{\text{eff}}(x_0) = V(x_0) - \frac{1}{\beta} \ln \zeta_0(x_0) - \frac{1}{\beta} u_f[x_0, \beta] \quad (78)$$

In practice, we first generate an optimal reference $\zeta_0(x_0)$ by defining a suitable frequency $\Omega(x_0)$ at each x_0 by optimizing the free energy. Thus PI-TCC theory includes the effect of quantum fluctuation around the classical centroid path in a nonperturbative manner. In other words, it is a nonperturbative theory of calculating the effective classical potential, $V_{\text{eff}}(x_0)$. Being nonperturbative in nature, PI-TCC theory works well at relatively low temperature regime where the quantum fluctuation is quite high.

Calculation of the grand partition function (gpf) of the double well potential

The system Hamiltonian :

Let us apply the PI-TCC formalism for computing the gpf of the one-dimensional double-well potentials for wide

ranges of coupling constant and temperature. For this we consider the following generic hamiltonian

$$H = \frac{\dot{x}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2}x^2 + \epsilon x^2 + \lambda x^4 + \eta x + d = \frac{\dot{x}^2}{2} + V(x) \quad (79)$$

where we have taken the unperturbed frequency to be unity. This will in turn generate the fluctuation part of the Hamiltonian $H_f(x_0)$:

$$H_f(x_0) = \frac{\dot{y}^2(\tau)}{2} + \frac{1}{2}W^2(x_0) y^2(\tau) + \eta y + \gamma(x_0) y^3(\tau) + \lambda y^4(\tau) \quad (80)$$

where $W(x_0) = [1 + 2\epsilon + 12\lambda x_0^2]^{1/2}$ and $\gamma(x_0) = 4\lambda x_0$. The corresponding classical component is given by

$$V(x_0) = \frac{1}{2}x_0^2 + \epsilon x_0^2 + \lambda x_0^4 + \eta x_0 + d \quad (81)$$

Hereafter, we shall omit the imaginary-time argument ‘ τ ’ in y .

Since the fluctuation variables y and \dot{y} satisfy the same commutation relation as the quantum variables x and \dot{x} does, they are related to the creation and annihilation operator of the quantum field theory as

$$y = y_+ + y_- = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2W(x_0)}} [\bar{y}_+ + \bar{y}_-] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2W(x_0)}} [a^\dagger + a] \quad (82)$$

$$\dot{y} = \dot{y}_+ + \dot{y}_- = i\sqrt{\frac{W(x_0)}{2}} [\bar{y}_+ - \bar{y}_-] = i\sqrt{\frac{W(x_0)}{2}} [a^\dagger - a] \quad (83)$$

It is to be noted that the creation operator, a^\dagger , is identified as \bar{y}_+ and the annihilation operator, a , is identified as \bar{y}_- . Thus, in terms of \bar{y}_+/\bar{y}_- the hamiltonian in eq. (80) takes the form

$$H_f(x_0) = W(x_0) \left[\bar{y}_+ \bar{y}_- + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{\gamma(x_0)}{[2W(x_0)]^{3/2}} (\bar{y}_+ + \bar{y}_-)^3$$

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$$+ \frac{\lambda}{[2W(x_0)]^2} (\bar{y}_+ + \bar{y}_-)^4 \quad (84)$$

Local choice of a best Gaussian around the centroid : the local optimal thermal Hartree frequency

For the calculation in the strong coupling regime, the choice of $W(x_0)$ as the frequency of unperturbed hamiltonian is a poor starting point. Thus an optimal zeroth order unperturbed frequency is chosen by inducing a Bogoliubov transformation of the field variables \bar{y}_+/\bar{y}_- to some new variables and minimizing the unperturbed free energy with respect to the transformation parameters. The resultant optimal renormalized frequency is called as the ‘thermal Hartree frequency’^{5,6,10}. In PI-TCC theory⁷, the chosen optimal thermal Hartree frequency is at each centroid point vis-a-vis the parent TCC theory^{5,6}. This is thus a ‘local’ thermal Hartree frequency. Let us induce a Bogoliubov-like transformation of the variables \bar{y}_\pm to a new set of variables \bar{Y}_\pm such that

$$\bar{Y}_\pm = \sqrt{\frac{2W(x_0)}{(1-t^2)}} [\bar{y}_\pm - t \bar{y}_\mp] \quad (85)$$

Inducing the Bogoliubov transformation through eqs. (85) in eq. (80), defining a parameter $\theta = (1-t)/(1+t)$ and subsequently writing the resulting expression in y -normal order with respect to \bar{Y}_\pm , the hamiltonian $H_f(x_0)$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{H}_f(x_0) &= \Omega(x_0) \{ \bar{Y}_+ \bar{Y}_- \}_y + \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y \\ &+ \epsilon(x_0) \{ \bar{Y}_+^2 + \bar{Y}_-^2 \}_y \\ &+ \Gamma(x_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{3!} (\bar{Y}_+ + \bar{Y}_-)^3 \right\}_y \\ &+ \Lambda(x_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{4!} (\bar{Y}_+ + \bar{Y}_-)^4 \right\}_y \end{aligned} \quad (86)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \bar{Y}_+ \bar{Y}_- \rangle_y &= n_f = \frac{1}{2} \text{Coth} \left(\frac{1}{2} \beta \Omega(x_0) \right) \\ &- \frac{1}{\beta \Omega(x_0)} - \frac{1}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (87)$$

$$\Omega(x_0) = (2\theta)^{-1}$$

$$\left[W(x_0)(1 + \theta^2) + \frac{24\lambda}{[2W(x_0)]^2 \theta} (2n_f + 1) \right] \quad (88)$$

$$\epsilon(x_0) = -(2\theta)^{-2}$$

$$\left[W(x_0)\theta^3 - W(x_0)\theta - \frac{24\lambda}{[2W(x_0)]^2} (2n_f + 1) \right] \quad (89)$$

$$\Gamma(x_0) = 6\gamma(x_0)/[2W(x_0)\theta]^{3/2} \quad (90)$$

$$\Lambda(x_0) = 24\lambda/[2W(x_0)\theta]^2 \quad (91)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y &= W(x_0) \left[\frac{1 + \theta^2}{4\theta} \right] (2n_f + 1) \\ &+ \frac{3\lambda}{[2W(x_0)\theta]^2} (2n_f + 1)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (92)$$

The minimizing condition is obtained from the equation

$$\frac{\partial F_{0q}}{\partial \theta} = 0 \quad (93)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} F_{0q} &= -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln Z_{0q} \\ &= \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y + \frac{1}{\beta} [(n_f) \ln(n_f) - (n_f + 1) \ln(n_f + 1)] \\ &\equiv \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y - \frac{S_0}{\beta} \end{aligned} \quad (94)$$

S_0 is the unperturbed ‘entropy’. Thus, the minimization condition eq. (93) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial F_{0q}}{\partial \theta} &= \frac{\partial F_{0q}}{\partial \theta} \Big|_{n_f} + \frac{\partial \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y}{\partial n_f} \frac{\partial n_f}{\partial \theta} \\ &- \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{\partial S_0}{\partial n_f} \frac{\partial n_f}{\partial \theta} \end{aligned} \quad (95)$$

One can verify that

$$\frac{\partial \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y}{\partial n_f} = \Omega(x_0) = \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{\partial S_0}{\partial n_f} \quad (96)$$

So that we have

$$\frac{\partial \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y}{\partial \theta} = 0 \quad (97)$$

Using eqs. (92), (93) and (94), we have

$$\theta^3 - \theta - \frac{24\lambda}{W(x_0)[2W(x_0)]^2} (2n_f + 1) = 0 \quad (98)$$

For the double-well potential, the eq. (98) has an imaginary solution for θ instead of real positive value. But θ^2 is real. To get the real positive solution, we write $\theta = i\theta'$ where θ' is real and positive. With this transformation, the Hartree condition takes the form

$$\theta'^3 - \theta' - \frac{\lambda}{4} \text{Cot}\left(\frac{1}{2}\beta\theta'\right) + \frac{\lambda}{2\beta\theta'} = 0 \quad (99)$$

and all the other expressions are changed accordingly. Having obtained θ' , one can get θ and θ^2 and work with them.

On the other hand, the renormalized frequency, $\Omega(x_0)$ becomes

$$\Omega(x_0) = W(x_0) \theta \quad (100)$$

Note that the condition (eq. (99)) also makes $\epsilon(x_0)$ in eq. (89) equal to zero. This is the 'local' form of the thermal Brillouin condition¹⁰. Thus, the hamiltonian $\bar{H}_f(x_0)$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{H}_f(x_0) &= \Omega(x_0) \{\bar{Y}_+ \bar{Y}_-\}_y + \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y \\ &+ \Gamma(x_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{3!} (\bar{Y}_+ + \bar{Y}_-)^3 \right\}_y \\ &+ \Lambda(x_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{4!} (\bar{Y}_+ + \bar{Y}_-)^4 \right\}_y \\ &\equiv \bar{H}_f^0(x_0) + V_f(x_0) \end{aligned} \quad (101)$$

where $\bar{H}_f(x_0) = \Omega(x_0) \{\bar{Y}_+ \bar{Y}_-\}_y + \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y$, is the normal ordered unperturbed hamiltonian.

The corresponding PI based mean-field partition function, Z_{0q} , is given by

$$Z_{0q} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 e^{-\beta V(x_0)} \frac{\beta\Omega(x_0)/2}{\text{Sinh}(\beta\Omega(x_0)/2)} e^{-\beta\langle V_f(x_0) \rangle_y} \quad (102)$$

where $\langle V_f(x_0) \rangle_y = \langle H_f(x_0) \rangle_y - \Omega(x_0)(n_f + 1/2)$.

Beyond the PI-Mean-Field (PI-MF) via the PI-TCC method :

In order to include the nonperturbative corrections beyond the PI-MF approximation, it is necessary to evalu-

ate the $\left\{ \overline{V_f[x_0, y(\tau)]}, \exp(S_f(\tau)) \right\}_\beta$ contraction on the right-side of eqs. (74) and (75) using the optimized 'local' thermal Hartree frequency. Then one can solve for the cluster cumulants $S_{m,n}^{k,l}(\beta)$ and $u_f(x_0, \beta)$ from PI-TCC eqs. (74) and (75). For the time being, let us include all cluster operators $S_{m,n}^{k,l}$ upto the total rank of 4, viz. $m + n + k + l \leq 4$. A typical such term, for example, is $S_{1,1}^{1,1}(\beta)$ which in long hand can be expressed as $S_{1,1}^{1,1}(\beta) \{\bar{x}_+ \bar{x}_0 + \bar{x}_- \bar{x}_0\}_y$. $u_f(x_0, \beta)$ is the fully contracted number part, which survives the y -averaging and contributes to the fluctuation component of the gpf.

As a first approximation, let us construct the PI-TCC equations by truncating the exponential of the right hand side of the exact eqs. (74) and (75) upto linear terms and forming the linked diagrams by connecting them with the vertex of the perturbing potential, $V_f(x_0)$. The construction of the PI-TCC equations becomes convenient in terms of diagrammatic technique whose rules will be discussed in the next Subsection. The algebraic expressions corresponding to a few diagrams entering the PI-TCC equations for $S_{2,1}^{1,0}(\tau)$ and $S_{2,0}^{1,1}(\tau)$ are given by

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{2!} \frac{\partial S_{2,1}^{1,0}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} &= [V_f]_{2,0}^{1,0} e^{2\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_q S_{1,2}^{0,0}(\tau) \\ &- [V_f]_{1,0}^{2,0} e^{2\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_c S_{1,1}^{0,1}(\tau) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} [V_f]_{3,0}^{0,0} e^{3\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_q S_{0,2}^{1,0}(\tau) \\ &- [V_f]_{2,0}^{1,0} e^{2\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_c S_{0,1}^{1,1}(\tau) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (103)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{2!} \frac{\partial S_{2,0}^{1,1}(\tau)}{\partial \tau} &= [V_f]_{2,0}^{1,0} e^{2\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_q S_{1,1}^{0,1}(\tau) \\ &- [V_f]_{1,0}^{2,0} e^{\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_c S_{1,0}^{0,2}(\tau) \\ &+ \frac{1}{2!} [V_f]_{3,0}^{0,0} e^{3\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_q S_{0,1}^{1,1}(\tau) \\ &- \frac{1}{2!} [V_f]_{2,0}^{1,0} e^{2\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_c S_{0,0}^{1,2}(\tau) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (104)$$

etc.

Similarly, the algebraic expressions for the completely contracted diagrams entering the equations for u_f^a (the

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approximate number cumulant) are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
-\frac{\partial u_f^a[x_0, \tau]}{\partial \tau} &= \frac{1}{3!} [V_f]_{3,0}^{0,0} e^{3\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_q^3 S_{0,3}^{0,0}(\tau) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2!} [V_f]_{2,0}^{1,0} e^{2\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_q^2 n_c S_{0,2}^{0,1}(\tau) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2!} [V_f]_{1,0}^{2,0} e^{\Omega(x_0)\tau} n_q^2 S_{0,1}^{0,2}(\tau) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{3!} [V_f]_{0,0}^{3,0} n_c^3 S_{0,0}^{0,3}(\tau) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{3!} [V_f]_{1,3}^{0,0} e^{-2\Omega(x_0)\tau} (n_q+1)^3 \\
&\quad n_q S_{3,1}^{0,0}(\tau) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{3!} [V_f]_{1,2}^{0,1} e^{-\Omega(x_0)\tau} (n_q+1)^2 \\
&\quad n_q n_c S_{2,1}^{1,0}(\tau) + \dots \quad (105)
\end{aligned}$$

Note that in order to achieve a better numerical stability, the above PI-TCC equations thus obtained are transformed to the Schrodinger-like representation of the cluster amplitudes, namely, $\bar{S}_{m,n}^{k,l}(\tau)$ given by

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{m,n}^{k,l}(\tau) \{ \bar{x}_+^m \bar{x}_0^k \bar{x}_-^n \bar{x}_0^l \}_y &= e^{-(m-n)\Omega(x_0)\tau} \bar{S}_{m,n}^{k,l}(\tau) \\
&\quad \{ \bar{x}_+^m \bar{x}_0^k \bar{x}_-^n \bar{x}_0^l \}_y \quad (106)
\end{aligned}$$

The resultant differential equations are solved by using the Runge-Kutta with Predictor Corrector Algorithm. This will lead to the approximate value of $S_f^a(x_0, \beta)$ and $u_f^a(x_0, \beta)$. Finally, having known the cluster amplitude $u_f^a(x_0, \beta)$, one can evaluate the approximate quantum partition function, Z_{picc}^a by

$$\begin{aligned}
Z_{\text{picc}}^a &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\beta}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dx_0 e^{-\beta V(x_0)} \\
&\quad \frac{\beta\Omega(x_0)/2}{\text{Sinh}(\beta\Omega(x_0)/2)} e^{-\beta \langle V_f(x_0) \rangle_y} e^{u_f^a(x_0, \beta)} \quad (107)
\end{aligned}$$

and the corresponding $V_{\text{eff}}(x_0)$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
[V_{\text{eff}}^a(x_0)]_{\text{picc}} &= V(x_0) + \langle V_f(x_0) \rangle_y - \\
&\quad \frac{1}{\beta} \ln \left[\frac{\beta\Omega(x_0)/2}{\text{Sinh}(\beta\Omega(x_0)/2)} \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{\beta} u_f^a[x_0, \beta] \quad (108)
\end{aligned}$$

*The diagrammatics*¹³ :

The various n -body hamiltonian operators are depicted by the unfilled circles as vertices with incoming and outgoing full and/or dotted lines. The quantum variables are represented by the full lines. The classical variables are represented by the dotted lines. The full lines with arrows going out of a vertex (e.g. $\leftarrow O$) signify \bar{x}_+ . The full lines with arrows going into a vertex (e.g. $\rightarrow O$) signify \bar{x}_- . The dotted lines with arrows going out of a vertex (e.g. $\dots \leftarrow O$) signify \bar{x}_{0+} . The dotted lines with arrows going into a vertex (e.g. $\dots \rightarrow O$) signify \bar{x}_{0-} . An unfilled circle containing m number of \bar{x}_+ variables, n number of \bar{x}_- variables, k number of \bar{x}_{0+} variables, and l number of \bar{x}_{0-} variables attached with it is represented by $V_{m,n}^{k,l}$ hamiltonian vertex. Similarly, the various n -body cluster operators (S) are depicted by the filled circles as vertices with incoming and outgoing full and/or dotted lines. A filled circle containing m number of \bar{x}_+ variables, n number of \bar{x}_- variables, k number of \bar{x}_{0+} variables and l number of \bar{x}_{0-} variables attached with it is represented by $S_{m,n}^{k,l}$ cluster operator vertex. The lines and arrow convention for the S operators are the same as the V operators. Let us explain some handy rules for evaluating the $\overline{V-S}$ connected diagrams as stated below :

- in a contracted diagram the value of contraction for each solid line going from the V -vertex to the S -vertex (i.e. an internal line shown as $\leftarrow O \rightarrow \bullet$) is n_q and that for the line in the reverse direction is $(n_q + 1)$,
- for each internal dotted line either forward ($\leftarrow O \dots \rightarrow \bullet \rightarrow$) or reverse ($\leftarrow O \leftarrow \dots \bullet \rightarrow$) direction, the value of contraction is equal to $n_c [= 1/\beta\Omega(x_0)]$ with a negative sign (-),
- for any set of 'r' number of equivalent $V-S$ internal lines (solid/dotted), a factor $1/r!$ is multiplied,
- for each set of 'p' equivalent ' $S_{m,n}^{k,l}$ ' vertices a further weight of $1/p!$ is associated. This will be associated only with the nonlinear term VS^2 in the PI-TCC equations,
- in a diagram for a set of 'i' equivalent uncontracted ingoing lines (solid/dotted) in a vertex (either V or S), and 'j' equivalent uncontracted outgoing lines (solid/dotted) in a vertex (either V or S), a topological weight factor $(1/i!j!)$ is multiplied,
- finally, for a diagram containing the V -vertex with $(1/m!n!k!l!)$ $V_{m,n}^{k,l}$, a term due to interaction representation $e^{(m-l-n)\Omega(x_0)\tau}$ is multiplied.

Note that while contracting $V_{m1,n1}^{k1,l1}$ to $S_{m2,n2}^{k2,l2}$, one should keep in mind that the V -vertex is associated with a factor $(1/m1!n1!k1!l1!)$ and the S -vertex is associated with a factor $(1/m2!n2!k2!l2!)$.

Results and discussion

We present the results of our computed values of the partition function, Z_{picc}^a and the corresponding results of the free energy in Table 1 for the various values of the coupling constants, ϵ , λ , η , d and the temperature, $T = 1/\beta$. We have compared the results with that of the PI mean-field partition function, Z_{0q} and the exact one, Z_q . Our results are closest to the exact results particularly at very low temperature where the quantum fluctuation is high. The exact partition function have been calculated by knowing the eigenspectrum of H obtained by diagonalizing H in the harmonic oscillator basis of the unper-

turbed $H_0 = \bar{y}_+ \bar{y}_- + \frac{1}{2}$ or, equivalently $H_0 = a^\dagger a + \frac{1}{2}$.

At higher temperatures, the contribution of the quantum fluctuation is so small that even the results of the PI mean-field is good enough. It is clear from the results of Table 1 that our PI-TCC method agrees quite well with the exact results for a wide range of coupling and temperature.

Concluding remarks

In this paper, it is evident that the PI-TCC method performs well for systems describable by double well potentials that is suited for developing quantum transition state theories (QTST) for reaction rate¹². This method in essence replaces the thermal trace by statistical average involving a gaussian smearing with respect to both the classical centroid path and the fluctuation. The local nature of the description follows from choosing an optimal harmonic reference frequency for each point on the centroid path. The thermal cluster cumulant (TCC) approach has been invoked for the fluctuation component of the grand partition function via cluster expansion. To achieve this, the field theoretic tools such as normal ordering and Wick's expansion formula involving contractions with respect to the fluctuation variable are developed. In order to guarantee size-extensivity a normal ordered exponential Ansatz is introduced that ultimately include quantum corrections beyond the mean-field results as an exponential of a connected cluster amplitude. The possibility of a systematic inclusion of the higher rank cluster operators and also more and more nonlinear terms makes the method quite efficacious. Finally, the generation of PI-TCC equations is illustrated with the rules of diagrammatic construction of them in Subsection 3.4.

Table 1. PI-TCC results of partition function for the symmetric and the asymmetric double-well potentials for various values of ϵ , λ , η and d

ϵ	λ	η	d	T	Z_{0q}	Z_{picc}^a	Z_{exact}
-1.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.25	0.12268	0.12849	0.12788
				0.30	0.17622	0.18114	0.18098
				0.40	0.27925	0.28232	0.28254
				0.50	0.37287	0.37454	0.37497
-1.5	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.25	0.24496	0.26408	0.26034
				0.30	0.31660	0.33022	0.32879
				0.40	0.44050	0.44637	0.44745
				0.45	0.49473	0.49704	0.49994
-2.0	2.0	0.0	0.0	0.35	0.26520	0.27910	0.27733
				0.40	0.31830	0.32906	0.32831
				0.45	0.36769	0.37574	0.37578
				0.50	0.41372	0.41950	0.42021
-1.2	1.0	-0.2	0.3	0.30	0.08367	0.08645	0.08630
				0.35	0.12118	0.12362	0.12363
				0.40	0.16055	0.16254	0.16270
				0.45	0.20060	0.20211	0.20241
-1.5	1.0	-0.2	0.4	0.30	0.08675	0.09052	0.09011

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Table-1 (contd.)

				0.35	0.12571	0.12886	0.12879
				0.40	0.16668	0.16894	0.16933
				0.45	0.20845	0.20968	0.21066
-2.0	1.5	-0.3	0.6	0.30	0.04740	0.05119	0.05037
				0.35	0.07492	0.07847	0.07797
				0.40	0.10587	0.10886	0.10873
				0.45	0.13897	0.14075	0.14152

Z_{0q} denotes the PI based mean-field results; Z_{picc}^a denotes the PI-TCC results; Z_{exact} denotes the exact results.

Appendix-A

Evaluation of path-integral contraction, $\langle T[y(\tau)y(\tau')] \rangle$, at finite temperature :

The correlation function of the y variables at two different temperatures τ and τ' with respect to Gaussian path integral measure is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_f(\tau - \tau') &= \langle T[y(\tau)y(\tau')] \rangle \\
 &= \frac{\int D[y] e^{-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 \right] d\tau} T[y(\tau)y(\tau')]}{\int D[y] e^{-\int_0^\beta \left[\frac{\dot{y}^2}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \omega_0(x_0)^2 y^2 \right] d\tau}} \\
 &= \frac{\int D[y] e^{-\beta \sum_{m=1}^\infty [\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2] |y_m|^2} \times \sum_{n=1}^\infty |y_n|^2 \times \left[e^{i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} + e^{-i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} \right]}{\int D[y] e^{-\beta \sum_{m=1}^\infty [\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2] |y_m|^2}} \\
 &= \frac{\int \prod_{m=1}^\infty \left[\frac{dy^{re} dy^{im}}{(\pi/\beta\Omega_m^2)} \right] \times e^{-\beta[\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2] |y_m|^2} \times \sum_{n=1}^\infty |y_n|^2 \times \left[e^{i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} + e^{-i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} \right]}{\int \prod_{m=1}^\infty \left[\frac{dy^{re} dy^{im}}{(\pi/\beta\Omega_m^2)} \right] \times e^{-\beta[\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2] |y_m|^2}} \\
 &= \frac{2 \times \sum_{n=1}^\infty \prod_{m=1}^\infty [I_m] \times [J_n] \times \left[e^{i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} + e^{-i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} \right]}{\prod_{m=1}^\infty \left[\int dy_m^{re} \times e^{-\beta[\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2] (y_m^{re})^2} \right]}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{\prod_{m=1}^\infty \left[\frac{\pi}{\beta(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2)} \right] \times 2 \times \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left[\frac{\pi}{\beta(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_n^2)} \right] \times \left[e^{i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} + e^{-i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} \right]}{\prod_{m=1}^\infty \left[\frac{\pi}{\beta(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2)} \right]} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left[e^{i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} + e^{-i\Omega_n(\tau-\tau')} \right] \times \left[\frac{1}{\beta(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_n^2)} \right] \\
 &= \frac{2}{\beta} \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left[\frac{\text{Cos } \Omega_n |\tau-\tau'|}{(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_n^2)} \right] \\
 &= \frac{2}{\beta} \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{\text{Cos } n \left[\frac{2\pi}{\beta} |\tau-\tau'| \right]}{[\omega_0(x_0)^2 + n^2 (4\pi^2 / \beta^2)]} \\
 &= \frac{\beta^2}{4\pi^2} \frac{2}{\beta} \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{\text{Cos } n \left[\frac{2\pi}{\beta} |\tau-\tau'| \right]}{n^2 + (\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2\pi)^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{\beta}{2\pi^2} \left\{ \frac{\pi \operatorname{Cosh} \left[\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2\pi} \left(\pi - \frac{2\pi}{\beta} |\tau - \tau'| \right) \right]}{2 \frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2\pi} \operatorname{Sinh} \left(\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2\pi} \cdot \pi \right)} \right\} - \frac{1}{2 \cdot \left(\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2\pi} \right)^2} \quad (109)$$

where

$$I_m = \int dy_m^{im} e^{-\beta[\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2](y_m^{im})^2} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\beta(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2)}} \\ J_n = \int dy_n^{re} e^{-\beta[\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_n^2](y_n^{re})^2} \times (y_n^{re})^2 = \frac{1}{2\beta(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_n^2)} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{\beta(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_n^2)}}$$

and $\omega_0(x_0)$ is the optimum frequency at each centroid point x_0 , $\Omega_m = (2\pi m/\beta)$ are the Matsubara frequencies as mentioned in eq. (39), and $0 \leq (2\pi/\beta)|\tau - \tau'| \leq 2\pi$, i.e. $0 \leq |\tau - \tau'| \leq \beta$. Therefore, we have from eq. (109)

$$G_f(\tau, \tau') = \frac{\operatorname{Cosh} [(\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2) - \omega_0(x_0)|\tau - \tau'|]}{2\omega_0(x_0) \operatorname{Sinh} (\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2)} - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} = \frac{\operatorname{Cosh} \left[\omega_0(x_0)|\tau - \tau'| - \frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2} \right]}{2\omega_0(x_0) \operatorname{Sinh} \left(\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2} \right)} - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \quad (110)$$

For the special case for which $\tau' = 0$, we have

$$G_f(\tau, 0) = G_f(\tau) = \langle y(\tau)y(0) \rangle$$

$$= \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} [e^{i\Omega_m \tau} + e^{-i\Omega_m \tau}] \times \left[\frac{1}{(\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2)} \right] = \frac{\operatorname{Cosh} [\omega_0(x_0)\tau - (\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2)]}{2\omega_0(x_0) \operatorname{Sinh} (\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2)} - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \quad (111)$$

From eq. (111), we have

$$\langle \bar{Y}_+ \bar{Y}_- \rangle_y = n_f = \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{Coth} \left(\frac{1}{2} \beta \Omega(x_0) \right) - \frac{1}{\beta \Omega(x_0)} - \frac{1}{2} \quad (112)$$

where $\Omega(x_0)$ is the renormalized frequency shown in eq. (100).

Let us calculate the Fourier amplitude of the temperature Green's function, $G_f(\tau, \tau' = 0) \equiv G_f(\tau)$ as shown below :

$$G_f(\Omega_m) = \int_0^\beta G_f(\tau) e^{i\Omega_m \tau} d\tau = \int_0^\beta \left[\frac{K}{2} \left\{ e^{\omega_0(x_0)\tau - \frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} + e^{-\omega_0(x_0)\tau + \frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} \right\} - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \right] e^{i\Omega_m \tau} d\tau = \frac{K}{2} \times \int_0^\beta \left\{ e^{-\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} e^{(\omega_0(x_0) + i\Omega_m)\tau} + e^{\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} e^{-(\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m)\tau} \right\} d\tau$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
& - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \int_0^\beta e^{i\Omega_m\tau} d\tau \\
& = \frac{K}{2} \times \left\{ \frac{e^{\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} e^{i\Omega_m\beta} - e^{-\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}}}{\omega_0(x_0) + i\Omega_m} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{e^{-\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} e^{i\Omega_m\beta} - e^{\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right\} \\
& = \frac{K}{2} \times \left\{ e^{\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0) + i\Omega_m} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right) - e^{-\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left(\frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0) + i\Omega_m} + \frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right) \right\} \\
& = \frac{K}{2} \times \left(e^{\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} - e^{-\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2}} \right) \\
& \quad \left[\frac{2\omega_0(x_0)}{\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2} \right] \\
& = \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0) \operatorname{Sinh} \left(\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2} \right)} \times \\
& \quad \operatorname{Sinh} \left(\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2} \right) \times \\
& \quad \left[\frac{2\omega_0(x_0)}{\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2} \right] \\
& = \frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0)^2 + \Omega_m^2} \quad (113)
\end{aligned}$$

where $e^{i\Omega_m\beta} = e^{2\pi i} = 1$ and

$$K = 1 / \left[2\omega_0(x_0) \operatorname{Sinh} \left(\frac{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}{2} \right) \right]$$

Note that the fluctuation propagator $G_f(\tau, 0)$ can be ex-

pressed as the difference between the quantum mechanical propagator $G_q(\tau, 0)$ and its classical ($\beta \rightarrow 0$) limiting value $G_c(\tau, 0)$. This is shown below

$$\begin{aligned}
G_f(\tau, 0) & = A \times \left\{ \frac{\operatorname{Cosh} [(\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2) - \omega_0(x_0)\tau]}{\operatorname{Sinh} (\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2)} \right\} \\
& \quad - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \\
& = A \times \left\{ \frac{\operatorname{Cosh} [\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2] \operatorname{Cosh} [\omega_0(x_0)\tau]}{-\operatorname{Sinh} [\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2] \operatorname{Sinh} [\omega_0(x_0)\tau]} \right\} \\
& \quad - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \\
& = A \times \left\{ \operatorname{Coth} [\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2] \cdot \operatorname{Cosh} [\omega_0(x_0)\tau] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \operatorname{Sinh} [\omega_0(x_0)\tau] \right\} - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \\
& = A \times \left\{ \operatorname{Coth} [\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2] \cdot \left(\frac{e^{\omega_0(x_0)\tau} - e^{-\omega_0(x_0)\tau}}{2} \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \left(\frac{e^{\omega_0(x_0)\tau} - e^{-\omega_0(x_0)\tau}}{2} \right) \right\} \\
& \quad - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \\
& = A \times \left\{ (\operatorname{Coth} [\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2] - 1) \cdot \frac{e^{\omega_0(x_0)\tau}}{2} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + (\operatorname{Coth} [\beta\omega_0(x_0)/2] + 1) \cdot \frac{e^{-\omega_0(x_0)\tau}}{2} \right\} \\
& \quad - \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)^2} \\
& = A \times \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{e^{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} - 1} \right) e^{\omega_0(x_0)\tau} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left(\frac{e^{\beta\omega_0(x_0)}}{e^{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} - 1} \right) e^{-\omega_0(x_0)\tau} - A \times 2 \times \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \{ \langle x_+(\tau)x_-(0) \rangle - \langle x_{0+}x_{0-} \rangle \} + \{ \langle x_-(\tau)x_+(0) \rangle \\
 &\quad - \langle x_{0-}x_{0+} \rangle \} \\
 &= \langle y_+(\tau)y_-(0) \rangle + \langle y_-(\tau)y_+(0) \rangle \quad (114)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $A = 1/[2\omega_0(x_0)]$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle y_+(\tau)y_-(0) \rangle &= G_f^+(\tau,0) = A \times [n_q e^{\omega_0(x_0)\tau} - n_c^+] \\
 &= \langle x_+(\tau)x_-(0) \rangle - \langle x_{0+}x_{0-} \rangle \quad (115)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle y_-(\tau)y_+(0) \rangle &= G_f^-(\tau,0) = A \times [(n_q+1) e^{-\omega_0(x_0)\tau} - n_c^-] \\
 &= \langle x_-(\tau)x_+(0) \rangle - \langle x_{0-}x_{0+} \rangle \quad (116)
 \end{aligned}$$

with

$$n_q = \frac{1}{e^{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} - 1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_c^+ &= n_c^- = \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} = 2\omega_0(x_0) \times \langle x_{0+}x_{0-} \rangle \\
 &= 2\omega_0(x_0) \times \langle x_{0-}x_{0+} \rangle
 \end{aligned}$$

Comparing eq. (47) with eq. (115) and eq. (48) with eq. (116) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle x_+(\tau)x_-(0) \rangle &= \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \\
 &\quad \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m \neq 0} \frac{e^{i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} + \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=0} \frac{e^{i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right] \quad (117) \\
 \langle x_-(\tau)x_+(0) \rangle &= \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \\
 &\quad \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m \neq 0} \frac{e^{-i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} + \frac{1}{\beta\omega_0(x_0)} \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \left[\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=0} \frac{e^{-i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right] \quad (118)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let us define

$$\bar{x}_\pm(\tau) = \sqrt{2\omega_0(x_0)} \times x_\pm(\tau) \quad (119)$$

$$\bar{x}_{0\pm} = \sqrt{2\omega_0(x_0)} \times x_{0\pm} \quad (120)$$

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \bar{x}_+(\tau)\bar{x}_-(0) \rangle &= n_q e^{\omega_0(x_0)\tau} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=0} \frac{e^{i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \quad (121)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle \bar{x}_-(\tau)\bar{x}_+(0) \rangle &= (n_q+1) e^{-\omega_0(x_0)\tau} \\
 &= \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=0} \frac{e^{-i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \quad (122)
 \end{aligned}$$

In this connection, it is worthy to note that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &[\langle y_+(\tau)y_-(0) \rangle + \langle y_-(\tau)y_+(0) \rangle] + c.c.] \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \cdot \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \left[\left(\frac{e^{i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. + \frac{e^{-i\Omega_m \tau}}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} \right) + c.c. \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\omega_0(x_0)} \cdot \\
 &\quad \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (e^{i\Omega_m \tau} + e^{-i\Omega_m \tau}) \times \\
 &\quad \left[\frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0) - i\Omega_m} + \frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0) + i\Omega_m} \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} (e^{i\Omega_m \tau} + e^{-i\Omega_m \tau}) \times \\
 &\quad \left[\frac{1}{\omega_0(x_0)^2 + i\Omega_m^2} \right] \\
 &= \langle y(\tau)y(0) \rangle \quad (123)
 \end{aligned}$$

Eq. (123) is consistent with the eq. (111) derived above.

Appendix-B

A quantum generalization of Novikov's theorem¹³ :

For a functional $A[y(\tau)]$ of the classical Gaussian variables $\{y_i(\tau)\}$, Novikov's theorem holds good¹¹

$$\langle y(T)A[y(\tau)] \rangle = \int g(T, \tau) d\tau \frac{\delta A[y(\tau)]}{\delta y(\tau)} \quad (124)$$

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In concrete terms, this implies that in the process of taking the average, the variable $y(T)$ contracts with any $y(\tau)$ that may be present in $A[y(\tau)]$. The rest of the $y(\tau)$ -variables remain uncontracted, which is symbolically represented as $\frac{\delta A[y(\tau)]}{\delta y(\tau)}$. If $\{y_i(\tau)\}$'s are not classical but quantum mechanical operators, then they are non-commuting as in Section 2, and using the T -ordered products, we also still derive :

$$\langle T[y(T)]y(\tau) \rangle = \int g(T, \tau) d\tau \frac{\delta A[y(\tau)]}{\delta y(\tau)} \quad (125)$$

In eqs. (124) and (125), $g(T, \tau)$ is the value of the contraction $\langle T[y(T)]y(\tau) \rangle$. The operator derivative in eq. (125) is interpreted as for $A = T[y(\tau_1)y(\tau_2)y(\tau_3)]$,

$$\frac{\delta A[y(\tau)]}{\delta y(\tau_1)} = T[y(\tau_2)y(\tau_3)] \quad (126)$$

$$\frac{\delta A[y(\tau)]}{\delta y(\tau_2)} = T[y(\tau_1)y(\tau_3)] \quad (127)$$

$$\frac{\delta A[y(\tau)]}{\delta y(\tau_3)} = T[y(\tau_1)y(\tau_2)] \quad (128)$$

If $A[y(\tau)]$ is a normal ordered operator, $\{A[y(\tau)]\}$, then the average above is zero unless $\{A[y(\tau)]\}$ has just one $y(\tau)$ variable. If there are $ny(\tau)$ -operators in $\{A[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)}$, then we can generalize Novikov's theorem as

$$\langle T[\{y^{(n)}(T)\}\{A[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)}] \rangle = n! \int \prod_{i=1}^n g(T, \tau_i) d\tau_i \frac{\delta^{(n)} \{A[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)}}{\delta y(\tau_1) \cdots \delta y(\tau_n)} \quad (129)$$

Note that the eq. (129) is used to reduce operator equations with uncontracted y -variables as obtained in PI-TCC equations of the type

$$\{A[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)} = \{B[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)} \quad (130)$$

where both sides have n $y(\tau)$ -operators in normal order, to amplitude equations by eliminating y -variables.

Using eq. (129), we have

$$\int \prod_{i=1}^n g(T, \tau_i) d\tau_i \frac{\delta^{(n)} \{A[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)}}{\delta y(\tau_1) \cdots \delta y(\tau_n)} =$$

$$\int \prod_{i=1}^n g(T, \tau_i) d\tau_i \frac{\delta^{(n)} \{B[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)}}{\delta y(\tau_1) \cdots \delta y(\tau_n)} \quad (131)$$

A remarkable simplification can be achieved now if $g(T, \tau_i)$'s are factorizable into two time arguments :

$$g(T, \tau_i) = g_1(T)g_2(\tau_i) \quad (132)$$

Defining amplitudes $\bar{A}[Y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ and $\bar{B}[Y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ by the relations :

$$\bar{A}[y(\tau)]^{(n)} = \int \prod_{i=1}^n g_2(\tau_i) d\tau_i \frac{\delta^{(n)} \{A[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)}}{\delta y(\tau_1) \cdots \delta y(\tau_n)} \quad (133)$$

$$\bar{B}[y(\tau)]^{(n)} = \int \prod_{i=1}^n g_2(\tau_i) d\tau_i \frac{\delta^{(n)} \{B[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)}}{\delta y(\tau_1) \cdots \delta y(\tau_n)} \quad (134)$$

we obtain

$$\bar{A}[y(\tau)]^{(n)} = \bar{B}[y(\tau)]^{(n)} \quad (135)$$

We should note here that $\bar{A}[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ and $\bar{B}[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ have no $y(\tau)$ -variables left in them, since according to eqs. (133) and (134) all the n $y(\tau)$ -variables of $A[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ and $B[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ are differentiated with respect to all the n $y(\tau)$ -operators. This is the reason $\bar{A}[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ and $\bar{B}[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ are just amplitudes. Moreover, if $g(T, \tau_i) = g(T - \tau_i)$, then

$$g_1(T) \sim A_1 \exp(k_1 T) \quad (136)$$

$$g_2(\tau_i) \sim A_2 \exp(-k_1 \tau_i) \quad (137)$$

where k_1 is an arbitrary number.

Then the averaging in eq. (131) can be faithfully reproduced by an operator equation :

$$\{A[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)} \equiv \{y^n(0)\} \bar{A}[y(\tau)]^{(n)} = \{y^n(0)\} \bar{B}[y(\tau)]^{(n)} \equiv \{B[y(\tau)]\}^{(n)} \quad (138)$$

which is equivalent to eq. (130) in so far as the averages from eq. (131) are reproduced by the replacements of $\{A[y(\tau)]^{(n)}\}$ by $\{y^n(0)\} \bar{A}[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$ and $\{B[y(\tau)]^{(n)}\}$ by $\bar{B}[y(\tau)]^{(n)}$. Instead of working with the operator equation, eq. (130) it would then suffice to equate the amplitudes \bar{A} and \bar{B} as in eq. (135). We have made use of this procedure in Section 2 where properties of eq. (132), (136) and eq. (137) hold good.

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